

The Immediacy Of Now

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Abstract

A Conceptual Art Work. The basis of an aspect of the invention. The aspect is realized through embodiments that define the invention, and form the basis for the Patent. Being the basis for the product on the market – helping people feel good. Solving an aspect of a Social Challenge or Problem. Art Exhibition. Open Air.

Key Words

Art Exhibition, Conceptual Art Works, Open Air, Invention, Patent, System and Method, Social Challenge or Problem, Disconnectedness, Social Disconnection, Connection via Relationship, Connection, Social Connection, Social Enterprise.

1 Introduction

This paper expands on areas of “The Immediacy Of Now” (Version 1) of 3 February 2026 [1].

I present the contents of this paper with the intent of bringing positive value to people, to the world around us. In art, technology, science, and society.

This includes the context of my Art form Composition of Framework, with a Conceptual Art Work and Patent with that in it.

As background, search systems, such as search engines and AI systems, have been increasingly relied on like a trusted friend, by people around the world. In this way a search user is looking for connection to information, knowledge.

The World Health Organization, WHO Commission on Social Connection, produced the 2025 report “From loneliness to social connection: charting a path to healthier societies” [2]. As said by the Co-chairs of the Commission and Commissioners:

“Make no mistake – connection is not just a nice idea. It is fundamental. It strengthens communities, fosters cooperation and creates opportunities. Without connection, we will not succeed in solving the problems facing us today – whether they are public health, economic growth or social stability.” [3]

Research question [also called the Background question]. How can a search system, such as a search engine, or an AI system, most accurately answer a search term, and solve an aspect of disconnectedness?

This paper demonstrates solving the Research question with a Conceptual Art Work as part of a Unified System. That Unified System is my art form. The composition of that is shown. The Conceptual Work and all related aspects and embodiments are in harmony. This is a departure from the traditional meaning of Conceptual Art where a Conceptual Work was more important than the form of the embodiment. This paper presents the High Performance Conceptual Work.

1.1 Landscape of Art Movements

This is to provide some background context in brief, by showing some key moments in time, related to the artist in each case.

Note. Yes, there are many more artists around the world that could be listed here, expanding on the background context, but this section is to communicate some background context in brief, in the context of this paper.

Marcel Duchamp

Duchamp created the “Readymade”. By a process. He first did Bicycle Wheel (1913) [4] by fixing a bicycle wheel to a stool and setting that up in his studio. This was not presented in a gallery at that time. The creation of the Readymade and position of that was really developed by 1915.

In his own words:

“My idea was to choose an object that wouldn't attract me, either by its beauty or by its ugliness. To find a point of indifference in my looking at it, you see.” [5]

Duchamp later did Fountain (1917) [6] for the exhibition of the Society of Independent Artists, to be staged at the Grand Central Palace in New York in 1917. They advertised they would accept any Art Work for the Exhibition if the admission fee was paid. Duchamp paid that. And although they did not explicitly [verbally] reject it, they effectively they rejected it by not presenting it as part of the Exhibition.

And we see 87 years later that “*Fountain* was selected in 2004 as “the most influential artwork of the 20th century” by 500 renowned artists and historians.” [7]

Duchamp opened up new realms with the introduction of the Readymade. He became the founder of Conceptual Art from his designation process.

Mark Rothko

No. 18, 1946 [8].

Softened red, blue, white, connections and conversations.

Described later by critics as one of his “Multiforms”.

“Rothko himself described these paintings as possessing a more organic structure, and as self-contained units of human expression.” [9]

"Rothko described his new method as "unknown adventures in an unknown space", free from "direct association with any particular, and the passion of organism". Breslin described this change of attitude as "both self and painting are now fields of possibilities – an effect conveyed ... by the creation of protean, indeterminate shapes whose multiplicity is let be." "[10]

No. 10, 1950 [11].

In softened blue, yellow, white.

Rothko's "interest was only in expressing basic human emotions—tragedy, ecstasy, doom, and so on. And the fact that a lot of people break down and cry when confronted with my pictures shows that I can communicate those basic human emotions ... The people who weep before my pictures are having the same religious experience I had when I painted them. And if you, as you say, are moved only by their color relationship, then you miss the point." [12]

Rothko pioneered the process of abstraction of his emotion and experience for the viewer to connect with. The valency of his forms in communion with his authenticity.

Roy Lichtenstein

In a 1966 BBC interview Lichtenstein said "... these half tone dots uh represent three dimensions but to put these half tone dots these same two-dimensional symbols on an actual three-dimensional surface and to make a cartooned image the symbols of which seem to Associated let's say with a flat working two-dimensional surface was something that interested me quite a bit also the idea of doing say a sculpture of cups and saucers in the same material the cups and saucers are done in in other words ceramic was another thing which interested me quite a bit the heads are a little bit of a different problem because the original heads are not in ceramic it was another in a sense excuse for decorating a surface but a kind of interesting one to me and one that sometimes get into amusing contradictions between what is two-dimensional and what is three-dimensional ..." [13]

Brushstroke, 1965 [14] by Lichtenstein, shows big open movement represented by being frozen in time. The organic feel of the original texture translated into a flat plane.

"Lichtenstein would say that the Abstract Expressionists "put things down on the canvas and responded to what they had done, to the color positions and sizes. My style looks completely different, but the nature of putting down lines pretty much is the same; mine just don't come out looking calligraphic, like Pollock's or Kline's." [15]

When Lichtenstein's work was first on display there was backlash. It was described as "vulgar" and "empty" [16]. In 1964 a Life Magazine article title was "Is He the Worst Artist in the U.S.?" [17].

"Lichtenstein responded to such claims by offering responses such as the following: "The closer my work is to the original, the more threatening and critical the content. However, my work is entirely transformed in that my purpose and perception are entirely different. I think my paintings are critically transformed, but it would be difficult to prove it by any rational line of argument." "[18]

Lichtenstein's Untitled, 1969 [Paper Plate] [19] shows right there, the paper plate, with language into the realm of the ceramic. The high gloss, the rounded weight, the flat yellow red and blue. The blue dots speak a transition that is stark, like notice. Giving a narrative of the transition. A 3D product now immortalised as paper.

Lichtenstein makes the connection between highly charged subject matter and its abstraction. The wholesome magnification of his technique giving a narrative of what's happening in the design.

2 Methods

2.1 The Conceptual Position

If the Work [which means the Conceptual Work, or the Conceptual Art Work] is the rhythm of the heart, the embodiments are the body. All elements and parts work together for the functioning whole that is the body. The Conceptual Work and its related aspect/s and embodiment/s of the invention, are all interrelated being of fundamental importance for the invention.

2.2 Implemented into Performance

Sol Lewitt declared

“In conceptual art the idea or the concept is the most important aspect of the work. When an artist uses a conceptual form of art, it means that all of the planning and decisions are made beforehand and the execution is a perfunctory affair. The idea becomes a machine that makes the art. This kind of art is not theoretical or illustrative of theories; it is intuitive; it is involved with all types of mental processes and it is purposeless. It is usually free from the dependence on the skill of the artist as a craftsman.” [20]

Unlike traditional Conceptual Art, where the idea is more important than the form or object, here each embodiment is a fundamental part of the Work. The embodiments show the mechanics to implement the Work into performance. The Work it to be made functional in the world by each embodiment being in harmony with it. In this way the Work is a High Performance Conceptual Work. Implemented into performance.

2.3 Harmonic flow through

The performance process fundamentally means that each embodiment and implementation must be in harmony with the Conceptual Work, as the harmonic system. This ensures the integrity of the system and method, or product, and its capacity to achieve the intention.

2.4 My Art Form [A Work]

A Conceptual Work

[in the context of The Composition of Framework]

2.5 My Art Form [The Composition of Framework]

- 1 Intention: To help people feel good, by
- 2 Solving the Social Challenge or Problem in an aspect [or more] and
- 3 Solving the Technical Problem, with
- 4 A Conceptual Art Work
- 5 As the basis for an aspect of the invention, where
- 6 The aspect is realized through embodiments that define the invention
- 7 As the basis for the Patent
- 8 As demonstrated in a Patent Application [that can include yet other additional aspects of the invention]
- 9 As the basis for the Patent [to be granted]
- 10 The Conceptual Work and its related aspect/s and embodiment/s of the invention, are all interrelated being of fundamental importance for the invention
- 11 As the basis for the System and Method, or the Product/s to be implemented, and used on the market
- 12 As the basis for people to use around the world
- 13 Where all items in this Composition of Framework are in harmony with the Conceptual Work.

2.6 Technical Problem

The technical problem area was conducted prior to 9 July 2023.

Search systems are heavily relied on by people around the world to connect to knowledge and other information. As such search systems are very influential in the lives of people, like a trusted companion.

If the search term yields search related material where the searcher feels they were not answered or they got an inaccurate output, then they can feel not listened to. This shows a disconnect. That is systemic. Not personal.

One way to summarise the technical problem is when the search term not most effectively answered. Or where the search results are inaccurate to the search, or are not accurate enough.

Now when a searcher feels listened to they feel good. Where they feel listened to because they are listened to. That's what we want. Connection.

Note. This is about robust technical research and is constructive is not about being non-constructive towards anyone's systems or products.

How can a search system most accurately answer a search term?

2.7 Social Challenge or Problem

Disconnectedness.

That includes Social Disconnection, or that can be interpreted as leading to Social Disconnection.

2.8 Reference to Social Challenge or Problem

With reference to the report from the WHO Commission on Social Connection, “From loneliness to social connection: charting a path to healthier societies” on page (xvi) under sub-heading “Key concepts” is the following:

“Clear definitions of social connection, social isolation and loneliness are achieving consensus. Social connection refers to how people relate to and interact with others. Social isolation, a form of social disconnection, is the objective state of having few roles, relationships and social interactions with others. Loneliness, another form of social disconnection, is a negative, subjective emotional state resulting from a discrepancy between one’s desired and actual experience of connection. How these concepts differ among cultures and along the life course is beginning to be explored.” [21]

In relation to technology the WHO Report states that the

“Use of digital technology to connect with others may reduce face-to-face contact, which offers more beneficial relationships (37). More research should be conducted on how digital technology alters social exchanges and what that means in terms of social connection.” [22]

2.9 Research Question

How can a search system, such as a search engine, or an AI system, most accurately answer a search term, and solve an aspect of disconnectedness?

2.10 Research

Having the finger on the pulse in the areas of:

- a. The Social Challenge or Problem
- b. Technical Problem
- c. Customer positions
- d. Trends and history
- e. Patents
- f. Operations in the market

2.11 Objective [for this stage of research]

Answer the Research question with a Conceptual Work in the context of the Art Form [2.5].

2.12 [Note} The Overall Project

Note. Where all items in the Composition of Framework [2.5] are in harmony with the Conceptual Work.

Though this paper does focus on the Deliverable of the Art Work, it is to be understood that all parts of the Art Form [Composition of Framework] [2.5] are in harmony with the Conceptual Work, and are interrelated with that. That is, all aspects and parts of the Art Form [2.5] are of fundamental importance.

Note. Following on from item 1, the time for the whole Composition of Framework [2.5] process being done is over a time period. The items are interrelated and taking that into account is part of the process.

3 Results

Conceptual Art Work.

a method of a top-level domain system comprising at least:
a term such as a search term connected via relationship with at least a part of search related material.

The Immediacy Of Now

Where is the Exhibition? Open Air. Around the world. What does this mean? The Art is online in Patent Applications, viewable via the links below. The Exhibition exists in the digital 'Open Air'.

When? From when the Patent Application is published. 9 January 2025 onwards.

What is the Art form? Conceptual Works. In the Patent Applications below with priority date 9 July 2023.

US Patent Application, Application Number US 18/750,836 [23]
<https://patents.google.com/patent/US20250013698A1>

AU Patent Application, Application Number AU 2024203741 A1 [24]
<https://patents.google.com/patent/AU2024203741A1>

There are numerous Works. There are 14 aspects of the invention, a separate Work in each. One of those 14 one is displayed below [as shown in the Results section 3].

Title: The Voight-Hanrahan Effect

Social Challenge or Problem. Disconnectedness.

Research question to answer. How can a search system, such as a search engine, or an AI system, most accurately answer a search term, and solve an aspect of disconnectedness?

Conceptual Art Work.

a method of a top-level domain system comprising at least:

a term such as a search term connected via relationship with at least a part of search related material.

Reference to the Patent Applications

As seen in the Patent Applications, US 18/750,836 [23] and AU 2024203741 A1 [24], this Work above is the basis of the 8th aspect of the invention. FIG. 26 and FIG. 27 with descriptions, demonstrate embodiments by way of example. These show the mechanics to implement the Work into performance.

This description of FIG. 26 speaks volumes:

“FIG. **26** shows a schematic diagram of an aspect of the invention, being a computer implemented method **260**. **26 a** shows one or more processors. **26 b** shows a search query term. **26 c** shows connection via relationship. By way of example, in this way, a search term **26 b** in a computer implemented system **260**, can lead to a connection via relationship **26 c**. This occurs where there is a connection of search related material including results, with the search query term **26 b**, being a term that self-similar or the same, present at the same time, in the search related material and the search query term. The relationship of the self-similar term is that of being a fractal. This is the process of connection via relationship **26 c**.”

This section from FIG. 27 captures the essence:

“The process of the computer implemented method **270** creating a fractal system **27 f** gives a computer user an interactive connection with nature. This interactive connection with nature occurs as the computing system **270** provides for input of the search query term **27 e** from a user, which is then echoed in the search related material, where the term there is a fractal of the search term. This shows the user helped create a fractal in the search related material. As fractals occur in nature, and this fractal process occurs on a computing system **270**, the user is connected to nature by the process of the fractal process occurring on the computing system **270**, and in the world around us at the same time. In itself this process can be seen as the computing system **270** with the connection via relationship **27 f** being a fractal of nature.”

4 Discussion

4.1 Social Challenge or Problem Solved in an aspect

The WHO Report on page 87 Fig. 14. shows “Three main causal pathways from social disconnection to health.” These are the “Interconnected Pathways” being “Biological” “Psychological” and “Behavioural”. [25]

The resounding solution gateway here is that they are “Bidirectional Relationships” [25].

Therefore, the base problem of Disconnectedness is solved by the process of Connection. The heart of this being connection via relationship. The searcher’s input is affirmed in the search related material, as a domain. The search results are accurate to the affirmed search term under that domain. Where the person making the input of a search term feels listened to because they are. Helping a person to feel good.

Empathy is a natural part of this process.

The flow on problem of Social Disconnection is naturally resolved in an aspect. The person is more connected with themselves and the world around us, which of course, includes people and Social Connection.

4.2 Technical Problem Solved

This can be described in various ways. For example, the search term is echoed in the search related material as a top-level domain, as a fractal, being self-similar or the same as the search term. Then there is knowledge-based content under the umbrella of the domain. The material presented is accurate to answering the search term, and is reflective of the world around us. Helping the person connect with the search system and the world around us at the same time.

4.3 Social Enterprise

The Art Form [Composition of Framework] [2.5] is the system of a Social Enterprise.

With the intention, in terms of a formalised business structure:

- a. The Purpose is in line with the Research question being solved
- b. Income is generated from commercialization of the Patent/s
- c. From profits, donate to people and causes.

5 Conclusion

A Conceptual Art Work. The basis of an aspect of the invention. The aspect is realized through embodiments that define the invention, and form the basis for the Patent. Being the basis for the product on the market – that people feel good using. An aspect of disconnectedness is solved – with connected via relationship at the heart. The Conceptual Work and all elements and parts of the invention are interrelated being of fundamental importance for the Patent. The Open Air Exhibition provides for open viewing of the Works for people to view if they ‘feel like it’. All IP Reserved inc Patent Apps US 18/750,836 | AU 2024203741 A1.

Further Works

I expect more papers will be done in the future looking at other Works in these Patent Applications, including the Work titled Habayashi Brooklands and Brookbank.

Acknowledgements

I thank the World Health Organization, including the WHO Commission on Social Connection, for sharing with the world their Report “From loneliness to social connection: charting a path to healthier societies”, 30 June 2025. This Report serves to help people around the world, and it has key data for this research.

I thank the late Marcel Duchamp (1887–1968) and The Estate of Marcel Duchamp for the creation of the "Readymade," and for Duchamp being the founder of Conceptual Art, with the intent to bring new value to concepts and connection via concepts.

I thank the late Mark Rothko (1903–1970) and The Estate of Mark Rothko for pioneering abstraction of his experience and feeling as elemental values. For creating new resonant forms with the intent to share his experience or feeling via an art work for a viewer to experience that.

I thank the late Roy Lichtenstein (1923–1997) and The Estate of Roy Lichtenstein for his special methods of abstraction. Including translating highly charged or emotive subject matter into abstracted depictions.

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[3] World Health Organization, WHO, 30 June 2025, Report from the WHO Commission on Social Connection, “From loneliness to social connection: charting a path to healthier societies” under heading “Foreword” p. v
<https://www.who.int/groups/commission-on-social-connection/report>

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[16] Lichtenstein, R., Wikipedia, under sub-heading “Breakthrough and Pop Art” paragraph 4, line 5 https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Roy_Lichtenstein

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<https://patents.google.com/patent/AU2024203741A1>

[25] World Health Organization, WHO, 30 June 2025, Report from the WHO Commission on Social Connection, “From loneliness to social connection: charting a path to healthier societies” p. 87, Fig. 14
<https://www.who.int/groups/commission-on-social-connection/report>

Definitions

These definitions apply to this document and to “The Immediacy Of Now” (Version 1) dated 3 February 2026 [1] and all related editions of that.

- a. “The Immediacy Of Now” (Version 1) [1] follows various editions made prior to that.
- b. “Being the basis for the product on the market” means being the basis of the product to be used on the market, or planned to be used, or that simply ought to be used, or is used on the market, stemming from the Patent, or under the Patent. This is not directed to products owned by other companies. This is in the spirit of noting the Art Work for people to view if they want to.
- c. “Work” and “Conceptual Work” means Conceptual Art Work/s.
- d. “Research Question” means research question and background question.
- e. “Open Air” means it is intended for open for viewing pretty much where air with internet connection ok. Or if there’s a problem with some air space, that blocks that, the spirit of it is that it’s like an Open Air concert viewed from the location of your space if and when a person chooses, and when they can connect in.

- f. “digital Open Air” means Open Air connected by digital technology. Or Open Air in the realm of digital space.
- g. “Open Access” for example used in The Immediacy Of Now (Version 1) [1] means: The Open Air Exhibition provides open viewing Access of the Works for people to view if they ‘feel like it’. “Open” in the sense that the Works are available for view around the clock, or “Open” to view if and when it suits a person. So, the Open Access is limited to viewing only. “Open Access” is not used to mean Open Source. And all IP Rights are Reserved. Note. The use of this term “Open Access” does not refer to the use of the term “Open Access” by Zenodo or other organizations.
- h. “Patent” means a Patent/s or a Patent Application/s.
- i. “All IP Reserved” means all IP Rights Reserved. That includes all Intellectual Property Rights and related rights are reserved that include the Patent Applications US 18/750,836 and AU 2024203741 A1.
- j. “for people to view if they ‘feel like it’.” Means freedom for a person to choose if they feel like viewing the Work or not. There are no mandates on when are person should or should not log on and view a Work. And there are no triplicate forms to fill in to aid or buttress that process.
- k. “Imaginary figure” or “Imaginary figures” means that creative license, or poetic license, has been used to identify an imaginary figure, or imaginary figures, or a fictional character, or fictional characters.
- l. “Preface. “They couldn’t stop laughing when they realized the sugar they were eating was actually flour.” [Said the imaginary figures, *E. A. & F. J. Mariner.*]” means a quote from imaginary figures.
- m. “Preface Bookend. “What’s more important. Left or Right?” [Said the imaginary figure, *Pomeroy.*]” means a quote from an imaginary figure.